

Lack of Information / Invariance / Conservation and Reflection/Refraction

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The idea of using a lack of information to solve a physical problem seems to often be linked to statistical mechanics. In particular, if one has a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas in a box with no potential, one may ask: Is there any specific information which would suggest a particle prefers one position point to another? There does not seem to be any hence density is constant in the gas. In other words there is a conservation law namely $\text{density}(\text{point A}) = \text{density}(\text{point B})$ for any A,B. A similar information argument may be made to describe the argument of the probability in the case of a potential. From classical mechanics $E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + V(x)$. Given E one cannot determine to which x point it corresponds. For a statistical gas, for a given E constant there is no information suggesting that probability should differ for any v,x pair which produces E. Similar arguments exist for other statistical results.

We argue here that an idea of a lack of information is not restricted to statistical mechanics. It may be present even in a conservation law such as conservation of momentum. For example, in (2) it is stated that conservation of momentum along the medium surface (say x) may be used to derive Snell's law. We argue that this is linked to an invariance in the x direction as the index of refraction n is only a function of y. n(y) carries no information about x and so we argue that this lack of information should manifest itself in a conservation law in the x direction. This idea may be extended to a mirror moving at constant v in the negative y direction. Again, the "medium" now only contains information about motion in the y direction. In (2) we have argued that this problem is like one with an index of refraction in the y direction, but this index does not depend on the medium, but on relative speeds of light and the mirror. Again there should be a conserved quantity. This quantity is the hypothetical velocity described in (2). It was previously shown that it is equivalent to the result obtained using Fermat's least time principle, but here we argue that it follows from a lack of information.

Thus we try to argue that a lack of information may lead to conservation laws and invariances in a wide range of problems. Being able to spot such an invariance may simplify a problem. For example, instead of using Fermat's idea of least time and taking a derivative of an expression for total time for both refraction and a moving mirror problem, one may simply identify the conserved quantity and write the final result in one line. One should note, however, that one must be careful in creating this conserved quantity. For example, in the case of the hypothetical velocity, it lies along the x axis, but represents a hypotenuse with relative velocities being a projection. It is not a projection of a given relative velocity (i.e. given information).

Lack of Information and Statistical Mechanics, Noether's Theorem

The idea of using a lack of information to solve a physics problem seems to be usually linked to statistical mechanics. For example, for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas in a container, there is no information which indicates that one position point is preferred over another. Thus one concludes that density is the same everywhere. This is of the form of a conservation law i.e. $\text{density}(\text{point A}) = \text{density}(\text{point B})$ ((1)) for all A, B. Usually in physics a conservation law is presented a priori as a fundamental idea. One might ask why all velocities in the gas are not of

equal weights aside from the $v dv$ solid angle difference. Again the idea of a lack of information comes into play, but one must incorporate some information that does exist namely the idea of two body elastic collisions. This is a constraint. Given this constraint:

$E = e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ etc should all have the same probability. There is thus a lack of information

as to which e_i, e_j pair (where $e_i + e_j = E$) one has for a fixed E and its associated probability i.e. $P(e_i)P(e_j)$ In other words:

$$P(E) = P(e_i)P(e_j) = \text{constant} \text{ i.e. a conservation law } ((2))$$

If one adds a potential $V(x)$ the idea of a lack of information again appears. From classical mechanics $E = .5mv^2 + V(x)$. For a fixed E one has a complete lack of information as to which v, x pair is represented. The same holds in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. Probability(v, x) is the same for all v, x which satisfy $E = .5mv^2 + V(x)$.

Thus we argue that a lack of information is a central concept which may be used to solve the Maxwell-Boltzmann gas problem even though other approaches are often used.

As noted above in nonstatistical areas of physics conservation laws are often presented as fundamental ideas i.e. the conservation of momentum. Noether's theorem (3), however, links a symmetry/invariance in a specific math function, the Lagrangian, to a conserved quantity. We argue that this is again the idea of a lack of information appearing which may be used to solve a physical problem.

Lack of Information in Refraction

In (2) Snell's law $n_1 \sin(A) = n_2 \sin(B)$ where n_1 and n_2 are indices of refraction and A and B the incident and refracted angles measured from a normal (e.g. y axis) with the medium being along the x axis is derived in at least two ways. First conservation of momentum in the x direction is presented as a given fundamental law. Secondly, Fermat's principle of least time is used. It is assumed that the incident ray hits the mirror at a point x starting from $(x=0$ and $y=Y)$. The refracted beam then moves to $y=-Y$ and $x_{\text{new}}=L-x$. Given that time = distance / $(c/n(i))$ and distance = $\sqrt{x^2+y^2}$ one obtains a conservation type result upon taking d/dx total time i.e. $0 = n_1 \sin(A)/c + n_2 \sin(B)/c = 0$.

In a previous note we argued that Fermat's principle is equivalent to introducing a conserved hypothetical velocity H in the x direction. H is not the x projection of the ray velocity, rather matters are the other way around. H is the hypotenuse and the ray velocity is a $\sin(A)$ or $\sin(B)$ projection. Then:

$$H \sin(A) = c/n_1 \text{ and } H \sin(B) = c/n_2 \rightarrow n_1 \sin(A) = n_2 \sin(B) \text{ } ((3))$$

Here we argue that such a conserved H should exist due to a lack of information. ((3)) is equivalent to conservation of momentum in the x direction if one multiplies both sides by momentum in a vacuum for which $n=1$. The argument goes as follows. The index of refraction is a function of y alone, not x so there is x invariance so from the point of view of the index of

refraction, which by definition governs the speed of light i.e. $c/n(i)$, thus there should be a kind of speed in the x direction which is conserved. In other words given the x invariance each x point is as good as the other for this hypothetical velocity H. This velocity is not a projection of the given information i.e. the ray information. Rather it exists a priori along the x axis. The ray information may be seen as a projection of this conserved quantity i.e.

$$H \sin(A) = c/n_1 \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(B) = c/n_2 \quad \text{with H acting as a hypotenuse and the angles being } 90-A \text{ and } 90-B. \quad ((4))$$

Thus one obtains Snell's law immediately with no a priori conservation of momentum law or Fermat's least time principle.

Mirror Moving at a Constant Velocity

Consider a mirror moving at a constant speed v in the negative y direction with the mirror surface along x. The goal is to calculate the angle of reflection in terms of the angle of incidence. This problem has traditionally been solved using either Fermat's principle or Lorentz transformations (see references in (2) and papers referenced therein).

We argued in (2) that the result of Fermat's least time principle is equivalent to a conserved hypothetical velocity in the x direction which acts as a hypotenuse such that

1/relative speeds along the ray motion are projections. One may note that 1/relative speed is equivalent to n i.e. $c/\text{relative speed} = n$. Thus we argue that a constantly moving mirror problem is of the same form as a refraction problem. Again motion information is only in the y direction meaning there is x invariance or a lack of information in the x direction. This information pertains to speed so we seek a conservation of speed equation in the x direction. This speed is again not simply a projection of the given speed information, namely the relative speeds along the ray. Rather the relative speeds are projections of H with $90-A$ and $90-B$ being the angles.

$$H \sin(A) = v(\text{relative A}) \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(B) = v(\text{relative B}) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{Where } v(\text{relative A}) = c - v \cos(A) \quad \text{and} \quad v(\text{relative B}) = c + v \cos(B) \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{Then } \sin(A) / v(\text{relative A}) = \sin(B) / v(\text{relative B}) \quad ((7))$$

The result may be written in one line.

Thus we argue that a lack of information in the x direction related to the mirror motion is equivalent to a refraction index which only exists in the y direction. The index of refraction by definition is linked to speed c/n so one looks for a conservation of a hypothetical speed in the x direction such that relative speed along the ray is a projection. As a result, a lack of information may be used to find a conservation law in a problem that is usually solved in very different manners. In other words, one might not expect a lack of information to be used in such a problem, but it seems to be used throughout physics, not just in statistical mechanics or Noether's theorem.

Conclusion

Although a lack of information is used in statistical mechanics to argue that the density of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas is constant and to also argue the maximization of entropy i.e. arrangements, we argue that it leads to conservation laws and may be found in many different areas of physics. In this note we examine refraction and reflection from a flat mirror moving at a constant speed in the y direction. These problems are usually solved using Fermat's principle or in the latter case also Lorentz transformations. Conservation laws are often thought of as a priori physical ideas. Noether's theorem uses the idea of invariance or a lack of information in a Lagrangian to obtain a conservation law, but this is often considered to be a mathematical procedure. We argue that this idea may extend beyond Lagrangians and suggest in this note that both the problem of refraction and reflection from a moving mirror may be solved by noting that the index of refraction and the motion of the mirror only depend on the y axis. Thus there is invariance in x. Both the index of refraction and motion of the mirror are related to speeds so we seek a conserved speed (hypothetical velocity) in the x direction. We do not have it be a projection of given information, rather we suggest that H act as a hypotenuse with the ray velocity or relative velocities being projections of the angles 90-A and 90-B where A,B are incident/refracted or incident/reflected angles measured from the normal. Then:

$$H \sin(A) = c/n_1 \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(B) = c/n_2 \quad \text{or} \quad H \sin(A) = v(\text{relative A}) \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(B) = v(\text{relative B}).$$

In other words both problems may be solved in one line based on the notion of a lack of information leading to a conservation law.

References

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3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Noether%27s_second_theorem